

Sharing PV generation in apartment buildings considering centralized energy storage system

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Abstract—Recent legislation enables electricity consumers in multi-apartment buildings to use electricity generated by their neighbors’ solar photovoltaic (PV) panels. The association of several residents with PV production (prosumers) is also allowed, increasing the value of the total installed production capacity, also increasing the scale factor of prosumers. This work explores shared self-consumption in a multi-apartment building, and based on real electricity production and consumption data, an optimization model based on Mixed Integer Linear programming (MILP) was implemented. The main goal was to minimize the electricity consumption costs from the external electrical network of each apartment, maximizing the benefits of non-production consumers in joining the self-consumption program, and maximizing the profits of prosumers. A sensitive analysis of total cost and prosumer/consumer benefit was evaluated. The obtained results show that prosumers and consumers can both have interesting financial benefits for participating in shared PV generation programs.

Index Terms—Energy Management, Energy sharing, Multi-apartments building, Optimization, Photovoltaic (PV) prosumer, Self-consumption.

I. INTRODUCTION

Producing and sharing photovoltaic (PV) solar energy with neighbors can be a way to save money and ultimately bet on renewable energy deployment [1]. In most countries, there has been an incentive, whether economic or environmental, for the final consumer in individual production (prosumer) and self-consumption [2]. However, new legislation (Directive (EU) 2018/2001) [3] allows electricity consumers in a neighboring relationship to organize themselves to produce, consume, share, store and sell surplus electricity [4].

Therefore, renewable energy self-consumers organized in building condominiums, communities of neighbors, in a close neighbor relationship may jointly invest in a larger PV installation, not only sharing the investment but also taking advantage of the different consumption profiles associated with the same production equipment, increasing the profitability of the system [5], [6].

In general, the collective self-consumption model is based on the association of consumers and nearby production units to

share electricity [7]. The Self-Consumption Management Entity (SCME), to be designated by its members, represents collective self-consumption in every relation with operators and administrative entities [8], [9]. Thus, the SCME is responsible for the relationship with the network operator (in managing energy sharing and making production data available), as well as for the relationship with the aggregator to sell surpluses from collective self-consumption.

The employment of energy storage systems [10], [11], or combined heat and power systems [12], jointly with PV solar generation is also explored to increase solar self-consumption and building self-sufficiency. The sharing of PV generation systems crosses the boundaries of buildings and can be profitable for the management of Micro-grids [13], [14].

Community solar systems have been considered to replace the traditional separate rooftop PV systems by residential consumers, electric utilities, and third-party renewable energy development companies [15]. Residential members who invest in community solar are likely to reap significant financial benefits.

Currently, there is a great interest in scientific research in studies focused on local energy sharing. In [16], an analysis of the profitability of the shared PV systems in multi-apartment buildings is proposed. A multi-objective optimization model was implemented for the optimal size of the PV system. Results show that the retail electricity price strongly influences the economic viability of shared PV systems.

In [17], the impact of switching from self-consumption to jointly acting renewable self-consumers on existing buildings in a city district was analyzed. A co-simulation platform was developed to support that analysis. Obtained results showed that the distribution of auto-generated solar energy results in self-consumption rates above 50% and self-sufficiency ratios greater than 20% over the load profile of all residents of the simulated condominiums. In [18], solar investment decisions are formulated under several pricing and sharing schemes as optimization problems that model the uncertainty arising from the energy consumption behind the meter and solar generation. In [19], the effect of sharing PV generation and energy storage within an apartment building was explored. Two energy sharing models were proposed, a welfare optimization, and a game-theoretical (bi-level) model. The obtained results showed

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that the optimization of building welfare allocates energy identically to the bi-level model with a discriminatory price auction.

In this paper, it is proposed a framework for sharing PV generation within an apartment building, with prosumers that have a solar PV generation system with the same installed power value. All the prosumers agreed to join their production and the neighbors without renewable production to participate in the shared PV generation program. A Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) was implemented to minimize the total electricity cost of each consumer, maximizing the incomes of prosumers. A Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) is considered to optimize the usage of renewable generation sources. The main contribution of this work can be summarized as follows:

- The financial impact for each apartment in joining the shared self-consumption program is evaluated;
- Based on the real database, an optimization model was implemented to minimize the electricity consumption costs, as well to maximize the profits of the prosumers and consumers;
- Taking into consideration the residential building context, the optimal value of the PV generation system is proposed;
- An BESS was considered into the proposed optimization model to improve the PV generation usage.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section II, the proposed shared PV methodology and the mathematical formulation in residential buildings are proposed. The case study and simulation results are described in Section III. And finally, the last Section IV provides the concluding remarks.

II. METHODOLOGY

We consider a residential apartment house in which various consumers live in the building, the prosumers that are owners of Photovoltaic (PV) generation and the consumers with out PV generation. Moreover, a Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) has been used to saves generated power from PV in the low-demand time and use it for home demand in high-demand time. The main idea of this work is to use the share PV strategy to analyze the allocation of energy resources in the consumers and owners. The setting for this case study is shown in Figure 1.

In the following section, an optimization framework is presented for sharing the PV generation among the customers to minimize the total cost of the building and maximize the benefits of consumers and owners. For the sake of clarity, The following basic assumptions of the proposed models have been considered:

- The prosumers have PV generators with the same characteristics;
- The PV owners agreed to join their production and the consumer neighbors participate in the shared PV generation program;
- The price for purchasing energy from the PV generation is known and is lower than the power grid tariff.

Fig. 1: Structure of Considering Residential Smart Building

The required parameters and decision variables in the mathematical formulation are all declared. The considered time period is supposed to contain D day(s) of duration τ time-step and let I represent all time-steps in the considered time period. The required parameters and variables are defined in Table I, which also includes their descriptions.

Note that $d \in \mathbb{D}$ denotes the day index in Table I, and $d = 0$ appears as indexes in certain variables and parameters. In fact, this indexes define the start time of the time period under consideration.

A. Mathematical Formulation for Shared PV Generation

In this section, the proposed problem is mathematically formulated by a Mixed Binary Linear Programming model that aims to maximize the self-consumption, profits of consumers and prosumers by using the shared PV approach to minimize the total cost of building. Lets, N_c is the number of consumers and N_o is the number of PV owners (prosumers).

The objective function in the proposed model is maximizing the benefits of consumers and owners and also minimize the total cost as:

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{z}) = \text{CB}(\mathbf{z}) + \text{OB}(\mathbf{z}) - \text{Cost}(\mathbf{z}). \quad (1)$$

where CB denotes the consumers' benefits are given as:

$$\text{CB} = \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^{n_c} (P_{PV \rightarrow B}(i,t) + P_{BE \rightarrow B}(i,t))(C_G^{\text{buy}}(t) - C^o(t)) \quad (2)$$

and the OB denotes the owners' benefits that is defined as:

$$\text{OB} = \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^{n_o} (P_{PV \rightarrow B}(i,t) + P_{BE \rightarrow B}(i,t))(C^o(t) - C_G^{\text{sell}}(t)) \quad (3)$$

The total cost of the building consists of the electricity consumption cost from the grid, the cost from using the shared

TABLE I: The List of Sets, Parameters and Variable.

Parameter	Index	Description
D		Number of days per time-study
I		Number of time-steps per time-study
J		Number of apartments in the building
τ		Time-step duration (hour)
$P_A(i, t)$	$i = 1, \dots, J$ $t = 1, \dots, I$	Power demand of apartment i at period t
$P_{PV}(j, t)$	$j = 1, \dots, N_o$ $t = 1, \dots, I$	Generated power by PV j at period t
S_{BE}^{\max}		Maximum State of Charge(SoC) for BESS
S_{BE}^{initial}		Initial SoC for BESS at the beginning of time-period
S_{BE}^{\min}		Minimum SoC for BESS
$P_{BE}^{\text{ch}}(t)$	$t = 1, \dots, I$	Active power related to the charging process of the BESS at t
$P_{BE}^{\text{diss}}(t)$	$t = 1, \dots, I$	Active power related to the discharging process of BESS at t
$C_G^{\text{buy}}(t)$	$t = 1, \dots, I$	Buying electricity cost from the grid at t
$C_G^{\text{sell}}(t)$	$t = 1, \dots, I$	Income of selling electricity to the grid at t
$C^o(t)$	$t = 1, \dots, I$	Buying electricity cost from the owners at t
$CP(i)$	$i = 1, \dots, J$	The contract power value for apartment i
Variable	Index	Description
$\alpha_{BE}(t)$	$t = 1, \dots, I$	Binary variable that represents BESS charging at t
$\beta_{BE}(t)$	$t = 1, \dots, I$	Binary variable that represents BESS discharging at t
$S_{BE}(t)$	$t = 1, \dots, I$	SoC of the BESS in the period t
$P_{G-B}(i, t)$	$i = 1, \dots, J$ $t = 1, \dots, I$	Active power from grid to apartment i at t
$P_{PV-B}(i, t)$	$i = 1, \dots, J$ $t = 1, \dots, I$	Active power from PV to apartment i at t
$P_{PV-BE}(t)$	$t = 1, \dots, I$	Active power from PV to BESS in period t
$P_{PV-G}(t)$	$t = 1, \dots, I$	Active power from PV to grid in period t
$P_{BE-B}(i, t)$	$i = 1, \dots, J$ $t = 1, \dots, I$	Active power from BESS to apartment i in period t
$P_{BE-G}(t)$	$t = 1, \dots, I$	Active power from BESS to grid in period t

PV for consumers and, the injected power in to the external grid as the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Cost}(\mathbf{z}) = & \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^J P_{G-B}(i, t) \cdot C_G^{\text{buy}}(t) + \\
 & \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^{n_o} (P_{PV-B}(i, t) + P_{BE-B}(i, t)) \cdot (C^o) + \\
 & \sum_{t=1}^T (P_{PV-G}(t) + P_{BE-G}(t)) \cdot (C_G^{\text{sell}}). \quad (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

In general, the full optimization model of the mentioned

problem in section II is described in:

$$\text{Max } \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{z}) = \text{CB}(\mathbf{z}) + \text{OB}(\mathbf{z}) - \text{Cost}(\mathbf{z}), \quad (5a)$$

$$\text{S.t. } \sum_{i=1}^J P_{PV-B}(i, t) + P_{PV-G}(t) + P_{PV-BE}(t) = \sum_{j=1}^{N_o} P_{PV}(j, t), \quad t = 1, \dots, I, \quad (5b)$$

$$P_{PV-B}(i, t) + P_{BE-B}(i, t) + P_{G-B}(i, t) = P_A(i, t), \quad t = 1, \dots, I, \quad i = 1, \dots, J, \quad (5c)$$

$$S_{BE}^{\min} \leq S_{BE}(t) \leq S_{BE}^{\max}, \quad t = 1, \dots, I, \quad (5d)$$

$$S_{BE}(0) = S_{BE}^{\text{initial}}, \quad (5e)$$

$$P_{PV-BE}(t) \leq \alpha_{BE}(t) P_{BE}^{\text{ch}} \tau, \quad t = 1, \dots, I, \quad (5f)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^J P_{BE-B}(i, t) + P_{BE-G}(t) \leq \beta_{BE}(t) P_{BE}^{\text{diss}} \tau, \quad (5g)$$

$$S_{BE}(t+1) = S_{BE}(t) + P_{PV-BE}(t) E_{BE}^{\text{ch}} - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^J P_{BE-B}(i, t) + P_{BE-G}(t)}{E_{BE}^{\text{diss}}}, \quad t = 1, \dots, I, \quad (5h)$$

$$\alpha_{BE}(t) + \beta_{BE}(t) \leq 1, \quad t = 1, \dots, I. \quad (5i)$$

$$P_{G-B}(i, t) \leq CP(i), \quad i = 1, \dots, J, t = 1, \dots, I \quad (5j)$$

that, the \mathbf{z} is the vector of decision variables in the proposed model 5 that are presented in Table I. In the above model, equation (5b) shows that the generated power by PV delivered to consumers P_{PV-B} , used for charging the battery P_{PV-BE} and inject into external grid P_{PV-G} . The equation (5d) indicates the balance between the consumption and generation of the building in each time slot.

The equations (5e)–(5i) represent the BESS constraints in which (5h) denotes the SoC updating of BESS in each time slot based on the charging and discharging process of BESS, by knowing the initial value of the charge condition (5e). The maximum and minimum capacity of the SoC is denoted by (5d). Moreover, the equations (5f) and (5g) limit the charging and discharging value of BESS. Note that, the binary variable $\alpha_{BE}(t)$ in these equations indicates the charging state of BESS in t -th time slot. In addition, the discharging state of BESS in t -th time-slot is presented by binary variable $\beta_{BE}(t)$. And finally, the constraints (5i) ensure that the charging and discharging of BESS do not occur at the same time slot. Moreover, the equation (5j) denotes the bound constraints for consuming energy from the external grid.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To illustrate the application and efficiency of the shared PV idea, we apply the proposed mathematical model (5) to a numerical example for a residential building contains 6 apartments with 3 consumers and 3 owners of PV generation with a capacity of 3.6 kWp.

Real data from the Iberian Electricity Market were used (www.omie.es/EN) that the value of power demanded P_A and the PV generated power P_{pv} are reported for every 15 minutes in which some data was not recorded. In this regard, a regression model and adjacent interpolation method are used

to fill the missing data. In this case, the considered time slot is one year with $\tau = 15$ minutes. So, the time-period contains $I = 96 * 365 = 35,040$ time-steps.

The following Table II lists the important parameters of the considered smart home in this work. At first, the proposed

TABLE II: Parameters Value of the Considering Smart Home.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
D		365	day
τ		15	Minutes
P_{BE}^{ch}		14	kW
P_{BE}^{diss}		14	kW
S_{BE}^{max}		28	kWh
S_{BE}^{min}		0	kWh
$C_{G}^{buy}(i)$		0.1614	EUR/kWh
$C_{G}^{sell}(i)$		0.04	EUR/kWh
$S_{BE}^{initial}$		40% S_{BE}^{max}	kWh

model is applied for the considered building to show how the model allocates power among the consumers. Then, the impact of the price C^o on the total cost, consumers' benefits and owner's benefits will be considered. Finally, a sensitivity analysis based on the size of PV generators is conducted.

A. The Allocation of the Energy Resources

In this section, the presented model (5) is applied for the considered building. The price $C^o = 0.1128$ EUR/kWh for buying the energy from PV by consumers is considered to characterize the optimal allocation of energy resources and the scheduled charging/discharging process of the BESS to maximize the consumers, PV owner benefits and minimize the total cost that are determined as:

$$CB = 477.5292, \quad OB = 716.2938, \quad Cost = 10,517.4371 \text{ EUR.}$$

The optimal allocated energy resources corresponding to $C^o = 0.1128$ EUR/kWh is plotted in Figure 2 for a sunny day. Moreover, the interactions among energy resources are specified by different colors.

Figure 2 shows how the model allocates energy resources to consumers 1, 2, and 3 and the owners 5, 6, and 7 during the sunny day. The owners share their own generated PV power with the consumers in the high-demanded time. Moreover, the extra PV-generated power is saved by the BESS in the high-demanded time (last plot in Figure 2) and is discharged to the consumers in the low-demanded time. Figure 2 indicates that the prosumers consume more energy from the energy resources than the consumers. This is because the energy allocation depends on the value of C^o . In this case ($C^o = 0.1128$ EUR/kWh), the more local energy allocation by owners leads more minimizing the total cost.

Table III reports the value of total cost and the consumer/owner benefits for three different values of C^o . The sensitive analysis of total cost and consumer/owner benefit regarding the C^o price is plotted in Figure 3.

The obtained results in Table III and Figure 3 show that by increasing the price C^o , the value of total cost and the owner

Fig. 2: Allocation of energy resources in consumers and owners for $C^o = 0.1128$ EUR/kWh in a sunny day.

TABLE III: Total cost, Consumer and Owner Benefit for Different Value of C^o

	No Share		Share PV	
	PV	$C^o = C_G^{sell}$	$\frac{C_G^{buy} + C_G^{sell}}{2}$	$C^o = C_G^{buy}$
Total Cost	10,598.55	9801.14	10,398.05	10,598.55
Owner Benefit	0	0	596.91	0
Consumer Benefit	0	1193.82	596.91	0

benefits increase as well but the value of consumer benefits decreases that is shown the good efficiency of the model. Note that, when the value C^o approaches the C_G^{buy} , the total cost is fixed and the value of consumer benefits and owner benefits is zero. This happened because the external grid supply also the power with the almost same price and is made the consumers indifferent between the external grid and PV generation.

B. Sensitivity analysis regarding the solar power capacity

Until now, It is assumed that the size of PV generations is fixed. In this section, the sensitivity analysis of the total

Fig. 3: Sensitivity analysis of total cost, consumer/owner benefit regarding the C^o price

price regarding the size of the PV generator is analyzed for three different prices C^o . The obtained results are plotted in Figure 4. Note that, the previously investigated PV size was $11.04 \text{ kWp} = 3 \times 3.68$ that is shown by a vertical line in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: Sensitivity analysis of total cost regarding the PV size capacity

The interesting observations are that:

- By increasing the size of the PV generation panels, the value of total cost decrease. Based on the value of C^o , the optimal size of PV generation is obtained. As it is shown in Figure, the optimal PV size for the considering building with $C^o = C_G^{\text{buy}}$ is around 46 kWp . If the value $C^o = (C_G^{\text{sell}} + C_G^{\text{buy}})/2$, then the optimal size of PV is 56 kWp . And also, the optimal size of PV generation for considering the $C^o = C_G^{\text{sell}}$ is around 61 kWp .
- By decreasing the price C^o , the optimal size of the PV generation is increased. This is because the allocation of energy is dependent on the price C^o . When the C^o is decreasing, then, the consumers try to more buy energy from the owner to increase their benefits. So, the owners need more PV size to support the consumers demand.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work an optimization model based on MILP was implemented, to support prosumers and consumers in multi-apartment buildings for sharing PV generation. Real data were used to analyze the financial benefits of all apartments. An energy storage system was also included to enhance the use of renewable production. Some important assumptions were done, mainly regarding electricity tariffs. For consumers, the electricity tariff from the consumption of PV generation should be lower, in comparison to the electricity supplier company tariff. For prosumers, who have PV generation facilities, the electricity consumption from PV panels should be free. A sensitive analysis of total cost and prosumer/consumer benefit was evaluated, as well as a sensitive analysis of the PV size capacity and total cost. In this case, the optimal PV generation capacity was achieved.

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